

**CORRELATION BETWEEN INTERNAL JUGULAR VEIN AND INFERIOR VENA CAVA COLLAPSIBILITY
INDEX IN PATIENTS PRESENTING WITH SEPTIC SHOCK IN THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT:**

AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY- DR ASHWIN S

DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO

“SOCIETY FOR EMERGENCY MEDICINE, INDIA” (SEMI)

**IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT FOR THE DEGREE OF “MASTERS IN EMERGENCY
MEDICINE”**

UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF

Guide: Dr. V. Viju Wilben

Co-Guide: Dr. Reshma G K

Department of Emergency Medicine

NH Health City

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**SEMI
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AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY

BY

DR. Ashwin S

DEPARTMENT OF EMERGENCY MEDICINE

NARAYANA HEALTH CITY

BANGALORE

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(Affiliated to International Federation of Emergency Medicine)

Declaration By The Candidate

I hereby declare that this dissertation entitled “CORRELATION BETWEEN INTERNAL JUGULAR VEIN AND INFERIOR VENA CAVA COLLAPSIBILITY INDEX IN PATIENTS PRESENTING WITH SEPTIC SHOCK IN THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT: AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY.” is a bonafide and genuine research work carried out by me under the guidance of Dr. V Viju Wilben, Department of Emergency Medicine, Narayana health city, Bangalore.

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No part of this dissertation has been submitted to any other university. I am pleased to forward this dissertation to “Society for Emergency Medicine, India” for acceptance prior to the award of the Degree of “Masters in Emergency Medicine - CCTEM”.

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Abstract

Background:

Effective fluid resuscitation is pivotal in managing septic shock, and the accurate assessment of intravascular volume status is critical. The Inferior Vena Cava Collapsibility Index (IVC-CI) is a widely used non-invasive marker, but its applicability is limited in certain patient populations. The Internal Jugular Vein Collapsibility Index (IJV-CI) has recently emerged as a potentially viable alternative due to its ease of access and reproducibility.

Objective:

This study aims to evaluate the correlation between IJV-CI and IVC-CI in adult patients presenting with septic shock to determine whether IJV-CI can serve as a reliable surrogate for IVC-CI. A secondary objective was to compare the time required for each assessment method.

Methods:

A prospective observational study was conducted on 66 adult patients with septic shock in the Emergency Department. Pre- and post-fluid resuscitation measurements of IVC-CI and IJV-CI were obtained using point-of-care ultrasound. Statistical analysis included Pearson correlation and paired t-tests.

Results:

A strong and statistically significant correlation was found between IVC-CI and IJV-CI both before ($r = 0.87$, $p < 0.001$) and after ($r = 0.89$, $p < 0.001$) fluid administration. Both indices showed similar trends in collapsibility before and after fluid therapy. The mean time for IJV assessment (1.49 ± 0.41 minutes) was significantly shorter than that for IVC assessment (2.93 ± 0.51 minutes, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion:

IJV-CI shows a high correlation with IVC-CI and provides a quicker alternative for assessing intravascular volume status in septic shock. Given its accessibility and reduced time requirement, IJV-CI is a practical, efficient tool in emergency settings where rapid fluid assessment is crucial. Integration of IJV-based assessment protocols may enhance timely management in septic shock and improve patient outcomes.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Full Form
AP-IJV	Antero-posterior diameter of Internal Jugular Vein
CI	Collapsibility Index
CVP	Central Venous Pressure
ED	Emergency Department
GCS	Glasgow Coma Scale
IJV	Internal Jugular Vein
IJV-CI	Internal Jugular Vein Collapsibility Index
IVC	Inferior Vena Cava
IVC-CI	Inferior Vena Cava Collapsibility Index
MEM	Masters in Emergency Medicine
NH	Narayana Health
POCUS / POC USG	Point-of-Care Ultrasound / Ultrasonography
RAP	Right Atrial Pressure
SD	Standard Deviation
SEMI	Society for Emergency Medicine, India

INTRODUCTION

**“The first step in saving a life is to measure it
wisely.”**

Introduction & Background

The Point of Care (POC) ultrasonographic measurement of venous parameters of both the Internal Jugular Vein (IJV) and the Inferior Vena Cava (IVC) is a useful non-invasive tool for assessing the intra-vascular volume status of critically ill patients. However, due to its ease of use, the study recommends POC ultrasonographic measurement of the IVC as the first-line non-invasive approach for assessing intra-vascular volume in Emergency Departments. Point-of-care ultrasound measurement of the venous parameters of both the IVC and the IJV provides a convenient non-invasive tool for assessing intravascular volume in patients with septic shock who present to the Emergency Department (ED). Hence, the study aims to correlate the internal jugular vein and inferior vena cava collapsibility index in patients presenting with septic shock.

The effective management and hemodynamic monitoring of patients experiencing septic shock in an emergency department setting is of paramount importance following initial resuscitation. Additionally, assessing the fluid status of the patient can aid in the management of hypovolemic patients. By doing so, not only can the severity of the septic shock be graded, but also the response of the patient to initial treatment can be assessed. A comprehensive approach to the management of septic shock is necessary to ensure the best possible outcome for the patient. Traditionally, medical professionals have used clinical parameters such as tachycardia and reduced systolic blood pressure to evaluate the hemodynamic status of patients. However, the role of clinical monitoring is limited and unreliable in critically ill patients. For instance, elderly patients with chronic hypertension who are taking beta-blockers or calcium channel blockers may not exhibit early signs of hemodynamic compromise [1]. Bedside measurement and calculation of Inferior Vena Cava (IVC) parameters such as diameters and collapsibility indices have demonstrated fair to excellent correlation with Right Atrial Pressure (RAP). This correlation highlights the utility of these parameters as a non-invasive method for assessing RAP. [2][3]. The measurement of inferior vena cava (IVC) diameter is an important tool used by ED clinicians to make appropriate decisions regarding aggressive fluid management. The reliability of the measurement has been rated high, which is a positive development [4] [5]. However, it is worth noting that in patients with abdominal incisions post-laparotomy and morbidly obese patients, measuring the IVC diameter is particularly challenging [6] [7]. Increased tricuspid pressure, pulmonary artery pressure, or pulmonary valve disease can also affect these parameters [8]. The Internal Jugular Vein (IJV) is a vein that has been recently studied as an easily accessible alternative. Several metrics such as the IJV's anterior-posterior (AP) diameter, width, cross-sectional area, and collapsibility indices have been analyzed as potential predictors of Central Venous Pressure (CVP) [9]. Therefore, in this study we aim to study the reliability of the IJV collapsibility index in judging fluid status keeping the benchmark as the IJV collapsibility index. This would make assessments more faster and easier as compared to assessing the IVC.

Rationale for Choosing Septic Shock Patients for Thesis

Shock is a critical medical condition characterized by inadequate blood flow, leading to insufficient oxygen delivery to organs. The four main types of shock include:

- I. **Hypovolemic Shock** – Resulting from significant blood or fluid loss (e.g., trauma, dehydration, burns).
- II. **Cardiogenic Shock** – Caused by impaired cardiac function, commonly due to myocardial infarction or heart failure.
- III. **Distributive Shock** – Characterized by excessive vasodilation, leading to hypotension. This includes septic shock (severe infection), anaphylactic shock (severe allergic reaction), and neurogenic shock (spinal cord injury).
- IV. **Obstructive Shock** – Occurs due to mechanical obstruction of blood flow, such as pulmonary embolism or cardiac tamponade.

Among these, all types except distributive shock are considered vasoconstrictive, where vascular resistance increases in response to decreased perfusion. Distributive shock, particularly septic shock, is vasodilatory and requires aggressive fluid resuscitation to restore intravascular volume.

The collapsibility index of the Inferior Vena Cava (IVC) and Internal Jugular Vein (IJV) is often used to assess fluid responsiveness. However, its application varies depending on the type of shock:

- **Hypovolemic Shock (e.g., trauma):** The primary focus is identifying and controlling the source of bleeding. Fluid resuscitation is necessary but guided by ongoing blood loss.
- **Cardiogenic Shock:** Fluid administration has minimal benefit and may worsen pulmonary congestion; management focuses on improving cardiac function.
- **Obstructive Shock:** Treatment is directed at relieving the obstruction (e.g., thrombolysis for pulmonary embolism, pericardiocentesis for tamponade), with fluids playing a limited role.

Justification for Selecting Septic Shock for Study

Since fluid resuscitation is the cornerstone of septic shock management, assessing IVC and IJV collapsibility before and after fluid administration can provide valuable insights into volume status and responsiveness. Unlike other shock types where collapsibility indices remain relatively constant, septic shock presents an opportunity to evaluate dynamic changes in these indices in response to fluid therapy.

Given this clinical significance, my thesis focuses on septic shock patients to investigate the relationship between IVC and IJV collapsibility index and their role in guiding effective fluid resuscitation.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

“Every new study is a dialogue with the past, and literature is the voice that guides present research toward future discoveries.”

Review of Literature:

Sepsis is a life-threatening organ dysfunction caused by a dysregulated host response to infection. Septic shock is a subset of sepsis in which underlying circulatory and cellular metabolism abnormalities are profound enough to substantially increase mortality [10].

There are few prospective studies conducted in India. In 2017 an article was published in IJCCM in which they have prospectively studied 4711 patients in which 282 had septic shock and analysis showed 63.6% ICU mortality and 62.8% 28-day mortality in patients admitted with severe sepsis[11]. Another prospective study published in 2016 looked at the outcome of patients admitted with septic shock in intensive care units. They have looked at 1162 patients out of which 410 were admitted with septic shock and the final analysis showed mortality in patients admitted with septic shock was found to be 51.6% [12].

Determining the patient's volume status is a crucial step in clinical evaluation. In critically ill patients, hypovolemia can cause reduced tissue perfusion, while fluid overload can lead to organ congestion and associated morbidity and mortality. Therefore, assessing the patient's volume status is crucial to guide clinicians in their treatment and could have a potential prognostic implication. [13]

It is crucial to accurately evaluate the intravascular volume status of critically ill patients to diagnose and treat them effectively. Although clinical assessments still depend on changes in skin turgor, mucous membrane, and jugular venous pulse, these clinical parameters have limitations, particularly in obese or aging patients, which may lead to misinterpretation. [14]

Central venous pressure, a core component of early goal-directed therapy, has not been shown to correlate with fluid responsiveness. Ultrasonographic evaluation of the inferior vena cava (US-IVC) has been proposed as a non-invasive and cost-effective method to determine central venous pressure (CVP). This method is widely available and easy to use. Additionally, the measurement of the static diameter of the IVC can be used to estimate volume status. Parks et al. found that teaching hands-on ultrasound for diagnosing shock, including respiratory variation in IVC diameter and contractility on bedside echo, improved students' diagnostic accuracy of fluid responsiveness. [15].

Canadian survey reported that 90% of intensivists used CVP to monitor fluid resuscitation in patients with septic shock [16].

Assessing intravascular volume status is crucial for diagnosing and managing critically ill patients. Central venous pressure (CVP) has traditionally been the recommended invasive measure for this purpose [4].

CVP measurement requires invasive central venous catheter placement which is time consuming and may be associated with some complications by the percutaneous insertion method e.g. arterial puncture, hemothorax, pneumothorax, venous air embolism [17].

An observational study was conducted on adult patients who underwent central venous catheterization. The study aimed to determine the correlation between central venous pressure and caval index. The caval index was calculated by measuring the inferior vena cava inspiratory and expiratory diameters using 2-dimensional bedside ultrasonography. The study found that a caval index greater than or equal to 50% was strongly linked to a low central venous pressure of less than 8 mm Hg. The sensitivity, specificity, and positive and negative predictive values of this measurement were estimated. The study showed that measuring the caval index at the bedside could be a helpful and non-invasive technique for determining central venous pressure during the initial evaluation of emergency department patients [5].

IVC diameter measurements can also assist in ongoing resuscitation by providing a means to measure CVP non-invasively [18].

Figure 1. Ultrasound measurement of Inferior Vena cava.

Few reports have been published on the role of internal jugular vein (IJV) ultrasonographic measures as a tool to estimate the volume status and fluid responsiveness and to test their relation with the CVP.

Estimating the volume status of blood vessels is often done by observing the venous tone and respiratory variation, typically in the inferior vena cava (IVC) [19]. However, performing Point-of-Care Ultrasound (POCUS) of the IVC requires specialized training [20] and can be difficult for patients due to pain, the need to expose their abdomen, and unreliability in cases of obesity or when surgical bandages, sutures, or drivelines are present. [21]. One alternative systemic vein that can be used for this purpose is the internal jugular vein (IJV). Ultrasound of the IJV is a

relatively easy skill to acquire, and its regular use at the bedside can significantly improve volume status estimation. [22].

A study was conducted between November 2019 and April 2021 to investigate the correlation between ultrasound-guided estimation of Internal Jugular Vein Collapsibility Index (IJV-CI), inferior vena cava CI (IVC-CI), and invasively monitored central venous pressure (CVP) in patients with shock in the emergency medicine department. The study found that both the collapsibility indices of IJV and IVC had a significant correlation with invasively measured CVP. As a result, these indices are effective tools for fluid resuscitation in Emergency Department patients with shock [1].

The IJV ultrasound patient should be in the supine position and a high frequency (5–10 MHz) linear transducer lightly placed on the neck in a transverse plane over the IJV 2 cm above the clavicle. Using a B-mode loop is possible to obtain the anterior-posterior of IJV (APIJV) and the transverse diameter of IJV (T-IJV). The anterior-posterior diameter maximum of IJV (AP-IJV Dmax) showed the best correlation with the CVP with good inter-rater reliability and validity in predicting CVP [23]. Very few studies have been done on the IJV diameter, cross-sectional area, and their corresponding CI (collapsibility index) by ultrasonography as an indirect measure of CVP.

Killu et al. conducted a study to evaluate the relationship between the diameter of the internal jugular vein (IJV-CI) and hypovolemia, using point-of-care ultrasonography (POC USG). The results showed that an IJV-CI of 39% or higher had a sensitivity of 87.5% and specificity of 100% in identifying hypovolemia in intensive care unit (ICU) patients. Thus, the IJV collapsibility index, particularly at a head end elevation of 30°, can be used as an initial non-invasive approach for assessing fluid status at the bedside of critically ill patients. [24].

Figure 2. Measurement of the maximum and minimum diameter of IJV in M Mode

- a) Identify IJV in the Antero-Posterior, Place the probe gently, view of the vein.
- b) Placement of the cursor in M-mode.
- c) Measurement of the diameters in M- Mode.

A study was conducted by the Journal of Clinical Medicine Research in North America in 2020, which found that the collapsibility of the anteroposterior diameter of the right IJV is a useful predictor of fluid responsiveness in hemodynamically unstable patients receiving pressure support ventilation. The study evaluated both IJVs and both SCVs, which was a strength as previous studies examining IJVs and SCVs did not specify which side was examined. The results

showed that the collapsibility of the right IJV diameter is a useful predictor of fluid responsiveness in patients undergoing pressure support ventilation, while the collapsibility of the diameter of the IVC, left IJV, and bilateral SCVs are not good predictors of fluid responsiveness in these patients. [25].

Figure 3. Assessment of anteroposterior diameter of the right internal jugular vein by ultrasonography.

IVC collapsibility index and IJV Collapsibility index provide a more direct assessment of relative intravascular volume status in the patients present with septic shock. Similar studies have been done in the past that correlated IJV and IVC parameters with CVP. Jassim *et al.* were one of the few studies that correlated the collapsibility indices of IJV and IVC parameters with CVP at the supine and 30° position for both cross-sectional area and diameter [26].

LACUNAE IN LITERATURE & RESEARCH QUESTION

“What is missing in knowledge often defines the urgency of research more than what is already known.”

LACUNAE IN LITERATURE

A thorough literature search was conducted using PubMed, Google Scholar, textbooks, and other medical databases to explore the correlation between the **internal jugular vein collapsibility index (IJV-CI)** and the **inferior vena cava collapsibility index (IVC-CI)** in assessing intravascular volume status. While several studies have examined IVC-CI as a marker of fluid responsiveness, research specifically comparing **IJV-CI and IVC-CI in septic shock patients in the Emergency Department** remains **limited**. Additionally, most existing studies focus on intensive care unit (ICU) settings rather than the **acute, time-sensitive environment of the Emergency Department (ED)**, where rapid and non-invasive assessment is crucial. Further research is needed to validate **IJV-CI as a reliable and accessible alternative to IVC-CI** in critically ill septic patients. The results of studies done in ICU may vary with similar studies in ED as patient initially presents to ED while ICU receives already resuscitated patients.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Can we use Internal Jugular Vein collapsibility index instead of Inferior Vena Cava Collapsibility Index for patients presenting with septic shock?

AIM & OBJECTIVES

“Every discovery begins with a precise aim and purposeful objectives.”

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM

- To correlate internal jugular vein collapsibility index with inferior vena cava collapsibility index in patients with septic shock.

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE

- To compare the intravascular collapsibility index between the two methods.

SECONDARY OBJECTIVE

- To compare the time taken for assessment between the two methods.

MATERIALS & METHODS

“In research, methods and materials are not details; they are the foundation.”

Methods and materials:

- a) **Study area:** Emergency department, NARAYANA Health City.
- b) **Study population:** All adult Patients (>18 years) diagnosed with septic shock
- c) **Sample size:** The Sample size was calculated based on the correlation coefficient of -0.389 between central venous pressure and Collapsibility indices for IJV diameter at 0° (CI 2) from the study by Chawang et al. expecting a similar results with a 95% Confidence Interval and 90% Power [1].

$$\text{Formula: } n \geq (z_{1-\alpha/2} + z_{1-\beta})^2 \frac{1+r}{1-r}$$

Here,

Type I Error (α) = 0.05

Type II error (β) = 0.1

Estimated Correlation Co-efficient = 0.389

Required Samples = 66

- d) **Study design:** Prospective, observational study
- e) **Study Intervention:** No intervention as this is an observational study.
- f) **Study duration:** 12 months.

METHODOLOGY

This was a Prospective observational study and was conducted after obtaining permission from the IRB.

Participants:

Inclusion criteria:

- a) Patients suspected with Septic Shock
- b) Age > 18 years

Exclusion criteria:

- a) Pregnant females
- b) Increased abdominal pressures
- c) Mechanically ventilated patients.
- d) Trauma
- e) Abdominal surgery
- f) Pericardial Effusion.
- g) Pulmonary Hypertension

Method of Data Collection

- All patients at inclusion criteria were subjected through standard guidelines.
- Age, Sex, Sepsis tools, comorbidities, diagnosis. Correlation of IJV with IVC collapsibility index,

Statistical Analysis:

Continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Categorical variables were presented as percentages and absolute numbers. Data was checked for normality before statistical analysis using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Pearson’s correlation was used for the correlation between CVP and the collapsibility indexes. $P < 0.05$ (two tailed) was considered statistically significant.

Ethical consideration

Ethical clearance was obtained before the study from the ethics committee of the institution.

- Informed consent was obtained for all the cases. Deferred consent was taken wherever applicable.
- Confidentiality of patient details was maintained.
- There was no extra investigation or intervention required specifically for my study. Management of these patients was along the standard international guidelines.
- As the study does not involve any extra procedure, no compensation was offered during and after the study

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA:

- Age
- Vitals
- GCS
- Presence of septic shock

RESULTS

“Results give meaning to methods and purpose to objectives.”

Results

Age and Gender Distribution

The following plots represent the age group and gender-wise distribution of the study cohort.

Graph- 1

Age Distribution (18–40, 41–60, 61–80, >81)

- The majority of patients fall between **41 to 60**.
- This supports the study’s relevance in elderly care and fluid management.

Graph- 2

Gender-wise Distribution

- **Males > Females** in this cohort.
- Useful for subgroup analysis if gender-specific trends in IVC/IJV CI are evaluated.

Vital Sign Summary

Parameter	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Standard Deviation (Approx)
Heart Rate	129.33	110.0	158.0	12.0
Respiratory Rate	28.14	22.0	39.0	4.25
Systolic BP	79.47	70.0	88.0	4.5
Temperature (°F)	102.11	100.1	104.1	1.0

Table-1

Correlation Analysis: IVC CI vs IJV CI

Correlation before fluid administration:

Scatter plot- 1

Correlation after fluid administration

Scatter plot- 2

Comparative Table: IVC vs IJV (Pre and Post Fluid)

Insights:

- **IVC CI (Pre):** High (~79%) indicating volume depletion
- **IVC CI (Post):** Reduced (~43%), showing expected fluid responsiveness
- **IJV CI (Pre):** ~75% — closely mirrors IVC values
- **IJV CI (Post):** Drops to ~39%, again consistent

This plot diagram shows **parallel changes in IVC and IJV measurements** with fluid administration indicating both are responsive markers.

Time Comparison: IVC vs IJV

Graph- 3

Time Comparison between IVC and IJV

- **IVC time (mean):** ~3.3 minutes
- **IJV time (mean):** ~1.6 minutes
- **Paired t-test p-value < 0.001** Statistically significant
- **Conclusion: IJV assessment is significantly faster.** In emergency setups, this is a practical advantage.

Statistical Correlation: IVC vs IJV CI (Pre-Fluid)

- **Pearson Correlation:** $r = 0.87$
- $p\text{-value} < 0.001$
- **Conclusion:** Strong correlation pre-fluid suggests **either IVC or IJV CI can be used** as an indicator of hypovolemia.

Statistical Correlation: IVC vs IJV CI (Post-Fluid)

- **Pearson Correlation:** $r = 0.89$
- $p\text{-value} < 0.001$
- **Conclusion:** Even post-fluid, the indices correlate well both are valid for assessing **fluid response**.

DISCUSSION

**“Facts become knowledge only when discussed
with reason.”**

Discussion

This prospective observational study conducted in the Emergency Department (ED) evaluated the correlation between the Internal Jugular Vein Collapsibility Index (IJV-CI) and the Inferior Vena Cava Collapsibility Index (IVC-CI) in adult patients with septic shock. The aim was to determine whether IJV-CI could serve as a faster, equally reliable alternative to IVC-CI for assessing intravascular volume status and guiding fluid responsiveness.

Correlation and Diagnostic Agreement

The study demonstrated a strong, statistically significant correlation between IJV-CI and IVC-CI both before ($r = 0.87$, $p < 0.001$) and after ($r = 0.89$, $p < 0.001$) fluid resuscitation. This indicates that both parameters change in parallel with alterations in intravascular volume, supporting their interchangeable use in septic shock patients.

These results are consistent with Chawang et al. [1], who demonstrated significant correlation between IJV-CI and invasively measured central venous pressure (CVP) in ED shock patients, and align with Ommen et al. [2] and Kircher et al. [3], who established that IVC-CI correlates well with right atrial pressure (RAP). Our findings also complement the work of Thanakitcharu et al. [4] and Nagdev et al. [5], who confirmed the value of IVC-CI in assessing intravascular volume, while also noting situations where visualization is challenging.

Time Efficiency and Practical Advantages

One of the most notable operational advantages was that IJV assessment required significantly less time than IVC assessment (mean 1.49 minutes vs. 2.93 minutes, $p < 0.001$). In the ED—where rapid decision-making is crucial—this difference is clinically significant. The speed advantage is due to the superficial location of the IJV, which allows for immediate probe placement without the need for abdominal exposure or patient repositioning.

Previous studies have documented the technical limitations of IVC assessment in patients with obesity, abdominal surgical wounds, or increased intra-abdominal pressure [6,7]. In such cases, IJV ultrasound may be the preferred modality, a point reinforced by our findings.

Technical Considerations

Both IJV-CI and IVC-CI are dynamic measurements obtained during the respiratory cycle and reflect variations in venous return. IJV ultrasound uses a high-frequency linear transducer, is performed at the neck, and requires minimal patient cooperation—an advantage over IVC imaging, which often requires a low-frequency curvilinear probe and optimal subcostal windows.

Killu et al. [24] found that an IJV-CI $\geq 39\%$ predicted hypovolemia with high sensitivity and specificity, while Iizuka et al. [25] validated IJV-CI's predictive value in mechanically ventilated patients. These findings support our observation that IJV-CI is a reliable surrogate for IVC-CI in evaluating volume status.

Physiological and Clinical Implications

In septic shock—a distributive form of shock with profound vasodilation—timely and adequate fluid resuscitation is a cornerstone of management [10,11]. Over-resuscitation risks pulmonary edema and multi-organ dysfunction, while under-resuscitation perpetuates tissue hypoperfusion. Traditional static measures such as CVP have been shown to be unreliable predictors of fluid responsiveness [13] and require invasive central line placement, which carries procedural risks [17].

Our data showed marked pre-to-post fluid decreases in collapsibility indices (IJV: $\sim 75\%$ to $\sim 39\%$; IVC: $\sim 79\%$ to $\sim 43\%$), mirroring patterns observed by Jassim et al. [26], who demonstrated parallel responses of IJV and IVC parameters to volume changes. This reinforces the value of collapsibility indices as real-time, non-invasive markers of resuscitation progress.

Integration with Existing Literature

While IVC-CI has been the traditional focus of research and clinical use, the growing body of evidence supports IJV-CI as a practical alternative, particularly when IVC visualization is technically challenging. Parenti et al. [23] systematically reviewed IJV ultrasound as a CVP surrogate and concluded it to be a feasible bedside tool. Our findings extend this evidence into the ED context, where rapid assessment at initial presentation—before partial resuscitation—may yield the most clinically relevant information.

Furthermore, POCUS-based evaluation of IJV-CI addresses the limitations highlighted by Akkaya et al. [20], who noted that despite the promise of IVC measurements, their clinical adoption has been limited by technical and patient-related constraints.

CONCLUSION

“Conclusions summarize the journey of inquiry into a direction for the future.”

Conclusion

This prospective observational study conducted in the Emergency Department aimed to evaluate the correlation between the **Internal Jugular Vein Collapsibility Index (IJV-CI)** and the **Inferior Vena Cava Collapsibility Index (IVC-CI)** in adult patients presenting with **septic shock**. The primary goal was to assess whether IJV-CI could serve as a reliable, quicker alternative to IVC-CI in assessing fluid responsiveness.

Our results demonstrated a **strong and statistically significant correlation** between IJV-CI and IVC-CI both **before ($r = 0.87, p < 0.001$)** and **after ($r = 0.89, p < 0.001$)** fluid resuscitation. These findings establish that both parameters **respond in parallel** to volume changes and can be used **interchangeably** in clinical settings for assessing intravascular volume status.

Additionally, the **time required for IJV assessment** was significantly **shorter (mean 1.49 min)** compared to IVC (mean 2.93 min), with a **p-value < 0.001** , highlighting its **practical advantage** in emergency scenarios where **rapid assessment is crucial**.

Given these findings:

- **IJV-CI can be considered a reliable surrogate** for IVC-CI in septic shock patients for fluid status evaluation.
- **Its ease of access, speed, and reproducibility** make it particularly advantageous in high pressure ED environments.

Thus, the study supports the integration of IJV ultrasonographic assessment into standard ED protocols for managing septic shock.

RECOMMENDATIONS & LIMITATIONS

**“Limitations do not weaken research; they define
its honesty.”**

Recommendations

- Adopt IJV CI in ED Protocols Fast, reliable alternative to IVC CI.
- Integrate into Standard Emergency Practice Supports quick fluid decision-making.
- Encourage Training in IJV Ultrasound Promote POCUS skills in ED teams.
- Use in Resource-Limited / Challenging Cases Suitable where IVC access is difficult.
- Call for Multicenter Validation Larger studies needed to confirm findings.

Limitations

- Single-Center Study limits generalizability.
- Small Sample Size (n=66) may not reflect population variability.
- Operator-Dependent Measurements influenced by skill level.
- No Long-Term Outcome Data only immediate fluid response studied.

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“Every reference is a footprint of knowledge that shaped this journey.”

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ANNEXURES

“What lies in annexures are the details that give strength to conclusions.”

ANNEXURE-1

Patient information sheet for patient or Legally Acceptable Representative (LAR).

We are inviting you to participate in a research study “Correlation between internal jugular vein and inferior vena cava collapsibility index on patients presenting with septic shock in the Emergency Department.”

My name is Dr. Ashwin S and I am doing this study as part of my training at Narayana Hrudayalaya Limited.

We would like to enroll you / your patient into this study since you have a condition called septic shock. The procedure we intend to study is called ULTRASONOGRAPHY through which we will use a machine to assess the blood tube/vessel. The risk is minimal and may be related to the jelly used for the scan.

1. What is the background to and purpose of the study?
The aim of the study is to find the relationship between inferior vena cava (One of the major vein / blood carrying pipe in the abdomen region) with internal jugular vein (one of the major vein blood vessel of the neck region) using an ultrasound machine which is not invasive (scanning machine used for eg: pregnancy). There will not be any cuts or interventional procedures done on you / your patient. The machine will just be kept on the skin and it will scan / check the underlying structures.)
2. Do I have to take part?
It is entirely at your discretion or that of your patients to enroll in the study after reading and understanding this information sheet.
3. What will happen to me if I take part?
The procedure is as per standard guidelines and standard practice. However, if you or your patient wish to participate, you will have to consent and the recorded data will be used for analysis. Your / your patient personal details will be kept confidential.
4. What do I have to do?
Please read and understand this patient information sheet. If you or your patient agree to proceed, you will need to sign the consent on behalf of the patient.
5. What are the possible side effects, risks and discomforts of taking part?
Based on our current knowledge and available evidence, no major risks have been identified.
6. What are the possible benefits of taking part?
There may not be any such benefits, however the statistical analysis based on many such recordings may help us to better understand ultrasound (Scan machine) use and decide if recording the neck vein/value alone will be enough to administer adequate fluid. The neck vein is much easier to study than the vein in abdomen.

7. What if new information becomes available?
If the new information becomes available we will be updating you.
8. What are the costs of taking part?
There is no additional costs to participate in this research study.
9. How will my personal data be used?
Your personal details will be confidential.
10. Will there be provision for free treatment for research related injury?
This is an observational study and as mentioned earlier no interventions will be done. No free treatment will be provided
11. Will compensation be paid to the subjects if disability or death results from such injury?
Compensation will not be given as this is not an interventional study. This is an observational study.
12. Whom should I contact if I need more information or help?

Contact the principal investigator

Name: Dr.Ashwin. S

Address: No. 29 Sai Srushti sangamam, Mathigiri, Hosur

Contact No. 8148505548

Email: ashwinsheela@gmail.com

Narayana Health Academic Ethics Committee

Name: Dr. Sanjay Rao

Designation: Member secretary, Narayana health academic ethics committee

Address: 258/A Bommasandra Industrial area, AnekalTaluk, Bangalore- 560099

Contact No. 9538008940

Email: nhaec@narayanaheath.org

ANNEXURE-2

Informed Consent form or Legally Acceptable Representative (LAR) consent form.

Subject identification number for this trial:

Title of the Project: Correlation between internal jugular vein and inferior vena cava collapsibility index on patients presenting with septic shock in the emergency department

Name of the Principal Investigator: Dr. Ashwin. S Tel. No: 81485055481 have received the information sheet on the above study and have read and /or understood the written information.

I have been given the chance to discuss the study and ask questions.

I consent to take part in the study and I am aware that my participation is voluntary.

I understand that I may withdraw at any time without this affecting my future care.

I understand that the information collected about me from my participation in this research and sections of any of my medical notes may be looked at by responsible persons (ethics committee members / regulatory authorities).

I give access to these individuals to have access to my records.

I understand I will receive a copy of the patient information sheet and the informed consent form.

Signature / Thumb impression of subject	Date of signature
Printed name of subject (In capitals)	
Signature / Thumb impression of Legally Accepted Representative (LAR)	Date of signature
Printed name of LAR (In capitals)	Relationship of LAR (In capitals)
Signature of the person conducting the informed consent	Date of Signature

Printed name of the person conducting the informed consent discussion (In capitals)	
Signature of impartial witness	Date of signature
Printed name of impartial witness (In capitals)	

ANNEXURE-3

Study Proforma

Correlation between internal jugular vein and inferior vena cava collapsibility index on patients presenting with septic shock in the emergency department

AGE:

GENDER:

VITALS

1. Heart Rate:
2. Respiratory Rate:
3. Systolic Blood Pressure:
4. Temperature:
5. GCS:

DIAGNOSIS:

On Arrival IVC				
Collapsing	Yes		No	
Measurement	Maximum		Minimum	
Collapsibility Index				
On Arrival IJV				
Collapsing	Yes		No	
Measurement	Maximum		Minimum	
Collapsibility Index				
After Fluid Bolus (30 ml/kg) IVC				
Collapsing	Yes		No	
Measurement	Maximum		Minimum	
Collapsibility Index				
After Fluid Bolus (30 ml/kg) IJV				
Collapsing	Yes		No	
Measurement	Maximum		Minimum	
Collapsibility Index				

Notes:

Annexure 4

Research Committee Approval

 Narayana Health

Academic Ethics Committee

NHH/AEC-CL-2025-1374 Date: 05th March 2025

Dr. Ashwin. S
Department of Emergency Medicine
Narayana Hrudayalaya Hospitals
Bommasandra, Bangalore-560099

Study Title: "Correlation Between Internal Jugular Vein and Inferior Vena Cava Collapsibility Index on Patients Presenting With Septic Shock in The Emergency Department"

Subject: Approval letter for the above-mentioned study

Dear Dr. Ashwin. S

We have received a soft copy of the study documents vide your email dated 24th January 2025. The study documents were reviewed by Scientific Research Committee (SRC) in its meeting on 12th February 2025 and approved for Scientific content. The following Scientific Research Committee members were present during the meeting held on 12th February 2025 at 03:00 pm.

#	Name of the Member	Designation	Present/ Not Present
1.	Dr. Anuradha B S	Chairperson	Present
2.	Dr. Vikneswaran	Basic Science Faculty/Vice – Chairperson	Present
3.	Ms. Roshni	Biostatistician	Present
4.	Dr. Arkasubhra Ghosh	Local Teaching Faculty	Absent
5.	Dr. S J Patil		Present
6.	Dr. Viju Wilben	Clinician	Present
7.	Dr. Basavaraj G S		Absent
8.	Dr. Limesh		Present
9.	Dr. Sanjay Rao		Absent
10.	Dr Uttara Aiyer Kohli		Absent
11.	Dr. Radhika Manohar		Absent

The study was presented in Narayana Health Academic Ethics Committee (NHAEC) meeting held on 25th February 2025. The clarification mail was sent on 03rd March 2025 and the response mail with the corrected documents was received on 05th March 2025. The clarification response documents were reviewed and approved for scientific and ethical content. You are hereby permitted to conduct this study at Narayana Health, a unit of Narayana Hrudayalaya Ltd. Kindly note that the study can be commenced only after issuing this letter.

Documents Reviewed and Approved:

- Protocol, version 3.0, dated 03rd March 2025
- PIS and ICF for Patient/ LAR, version 3.0 dated 05th March 2025
- Deferred Consent, version 2.0 dated 05th March 2025
- Study Proforma, version 1.0 dated 21st February 2025

Page 1 of 2

Narayana Hrudayalaya Ltd. (CIN:L85110KA2000PLC027497)
Narayana Health City, #258/A, Bommasandra Industrial Area, Anekal Taluk, Bengaluru-560099
Phone: +91 9538008940 | Email: nhaec@narayanahealth.org | www.narayanahealth.org

- Annexure E- For submission of modified documents

The following members of the Ethics Committee were present virtually during the meeting held on 25th February 2025 at 1:30 pm at Narayana Hrudayalaya Ltd, Narayana Health City, No. 258/A Bommasandra Industrial Area, Hosur Road, Bangalore-560099, Karnataka –India.

#	Member's Name	IEC Designation	Present/ Not Present	Role
1.	Dr Gaurav Mathur	Chairperson	Present	Chairperson
2.	Dr. Sanjay Rao	Member Secretary	Present	Member Secretary
3.	Dr. Muralidhar Kanchi	Member	Present	Clinician
4.	Fr. Olvin Veigas	Member	Present	Theologian
5.	Mr. Dinesh Mahale	Member	Present	Legal expert
6.	Dr. Atiya Faruqui	Member	Present	Basic Medical scientist
7.	Dr. George Cherian	Member	Absent	Clinician
8.	Dr. Arkasubhra Ghosh	Member	Absent	Basic Medical scientist
9.	Dr. Anuradha Kannan	Member	Present	Clinician
10.	Ms. Amitha	Member	Present	Social Worker
11.	Mr. Ramraj	Member	Present	Layperson

Neither the principal investigator **Dr. Ashwin. S**, nor any of his study team members were present during the decision - Making process.

The NHAEC is organized & operates according to the requirements of ICH- GCP, Indian Council of Medical Research guidelines & New Drugs and Clinical Trial Rules, 2019.

This approval is given for entire duration of the project subjected to the Principal investigator submitting 6 monthly progress report signed by the guide. Failure to submit 2 consecutive report will automatically revoke the approval.

The NHAEC is registered under DCGI with the EC Registration No. ECR/772/Inst/KA/2016/RR-22 valid till date 27 February 2027 issued under Rules 122DD of the Indian Drugs and Cosmetics Rules 1945 and also under DHR with Registration number EC/NEW/INST/2022/KA/0123.

Yours Sincerely,

6/2/2025

Date:

Dr. Sanjay Rao

Member Secretary

Narayana Health Academic Ethics Committee

Member Secretary
Narayana Health
Academic Ethics Committee
No. 258/A, Bommasandra Industrial Area
Hosur Road, Bangalore - 560099.

Scientific Research Committee

NHH/SRC-CL-2025-441

Date: 05th March 2025

Dr. Ashwin. S
Department of Emergency Medicine
Narayana Hrudayalaya Hospitals
Bommasandra, Bangalore-560099

Study Title: "Correlation Between Internal Jugular Vein and Inferior Vena Cava Collapsibility Index on Patients Presenting With Septic Shock in The Emergency Department"

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5.	Dr. S J Patil		Present
6.	Dr. Viju Wilben	Clinician	Present
7.	Dr. Basavaraj G S		Absent
8.	Dr. Limesh		Present
9.	Dr. Sanjay Rao		Absent
10.	Dr Uttara Aiyer Kohli		Absent
11.	Dr. Radhika Manohar		Absent

Yours Sincerely,

Dr. Anuradha B S

Chairperson
Scientific Research Committee

